

NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS OF STANDARD MECHANICAL TESTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND OPTIMIZATION OF FULLY BIORESORBABLE STENTS

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Keywords: In vitro mechanical test, vascular scaffold, bioresorbable PLLA stent, design and optimization, finite element analysis

Abstract: Standard mechanical tests are required according to ISO standards for stents produced for the purpose of deployment within coronary arteries. The development of a stent design that successfully passes all experimental tests is a time-consuming, difficult and expensive process, which consists of several stages and requires many cycles of mechanical testing and redesigning of the basic model. On the other hand, in-silico mechanical tests could reduce the cost and the number of necessary real mechanical tests. In this paper we use a recently introduced material model of poly-L-lactic acid (PLLA) fully bioresorbable vascular scaffold and recently empowered numerical InSilc platform, in order to perform in-silico mechanical tests of different stent designs with different material and geometrical characteristics. In this work we compare and analyze the impact of strut thickness on mechanical characteristics of AB-BVS scaffold, as well as the impact of additional pocket holes (slots) in stent geometry on mechanical characteristics of Renuvia-PLLA stent. The numerical results and corresponding analysis are provided for each of the stent designs, and for four different tests: radial compression, inflation, three-point bending, two-plates crush resistance, local compression, kinking and flex.